

Biochar as a soil amendment

Biochar from wood-based materials is a charcoal with more than 60 identified uses when it replaces coal from the earth and peat. It has potential, especially as raw material for forest fertilizers, as it contains phosphorus, potassium and calcium, which are important nutrients for tree growth. It can be particularly used in degraded soils. It is used in greenhouse production and tree nurseries where it replaces growth peat. It is an efficient carbon sink as one metric ton of biochar binds 3.7 tons of CO₂ and carbon of biochar mineralizes 10 to 100 times slower compared to uncharred biomass. Furthermore, the technology is reliable and emission-free. It is a good use for wood residues and clean waste wood. More than 60 uses have been identified (e.g. replacing peat as a growing medium for tree seedlings). During manufacture, nutrient granules can be added to the biochar. Eventual potential risks regarding the formation of harmful organic compounds can be minimized by adapting the processes accordingly.

Regional coverage and transferability

Biochar for soil amendment has reached the commercial production in Northern and Central Europe. Biochar has the potential to enhance soil functions related to nutrient and water balance as well as soil reaction and productivity of high importance to fight climate change impacts on forest soils.

Images: Fernando Urbano Tenorio and Johanna Nikama (Luke)

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ Improves the capacity for higher value applications of wood residues beyond only thermal recycling
- ▶ The manufacturing technology is reliable and emission-free
- ▶ Improved biomass sustainability by optimized growing conditions and carbon sinks
- ▶ Carbon sequestration is a main innovation driver, which can enable many process, product, management and governance-oriented changes
- ▶ Improving public acceptance to think in carbon cycles is essential and will lead to improved sustainability
- ▶ Advances the legislative situation for carbon sequestration
- ▶ Contributes to tackle climate change!